

Catalytic Decomposition of H_2O_2 by Nickel, Sodium and Zinc Salts

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The catalytic activity of nickel, sodium and zinc salts, in the temperature range 25 to 80°, has been investigated towards the decomposition of aqueous H_2O_2 . It was observed that the rate of decomposition, obeyed 1st-order kinetics. Various salts exerted their catalytic effect primarily on the entropy of activation, the energy of activation remained almost the same. Nickel sulphate was the most active salt in H_2O_2 decomposition, but sodium sulphate was found to be completely inactive. The rate of H_2O_2 decomposition decreased by the combination NaOH + nickel or zinc sulphate. The catalytic influence of nickel chloride or nitrate almost disappeared on the addition of NaOH to the peroxide solution of these salts. A substantial decomposition of H_2O_2 occurred by sodium sulphate in media where pH values were greater than 8.

The catalytic decomposition of dilute solutions of H_2O_2 by salts and metal complexes has been studied by various workers^{1,2,3}. However, there have been comparatively few kinetic investigations in which the activity of various catalysts could be studied in the light of their effects on the energy and entropy of activation of the decomposition reaction.

Salts selected for such investigation were: nickel sulphate, chloride and nitrate, zinc sulphate and sodium sulphate, thus each of the salts contained either SO_4^{-2} or Ni^{+2} . In this way, it was possible to deal with only few types of ions and, also, to deduce the influence of each ion on the rate of H_2O_2 decomposition, mainly by comparing the catalytic action of salts having either the same anion or the same common cation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Hydrogen peroxide and the salts were of Analar quality, they were further treated to insure extra purity before use. Temperatures were controlled by a thermostat in which the temperature variation was less than 0.1°. A typical experimental procedure involved placing 0.1 equivalent of the salt in a flask which was suspended in the thermostat, and subsequently the reaction was initiated by the addition of 100 ml of 0.15*M* hydrogen peroxide solution. The rate of the decomposition was followed by titrating the undecomposed hydrogen peroxide with a standard solution of potassium permanganate in presence of sulphuric acid. At the end of each run, a quantitative determination of the concentration of each salt was performed using samples of the remaining experimental solutions. No change in salt concentration was observed in any case. Moreover, samples of the experimental solutions were taken at the end of each experiment for pH measurements using a PYE type pH -emter.

1. Kremer, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1963, **59**, 2535.
2. Petri, Sigel and Erlonmeyer, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1966, **49**, 1778.
3. Bogdanow and Pastukhov, *Zhur Fiz Khim.*, 1953, **27**, 1556.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Nickel, sodium and zinc salts vary in their effects on the rate of decomposition of H₂O₂; in the temperature range 25 to 80°, nickel sulphate was the most, and sodium sulphate the least, effective salt in decomposing the peroxide. These results, together with those obtained with remaining salts, at 60° are shown in fig 1.

An increase in the concentration of H₂O₂, at the same concentration of the salt, by a factor of 2 or 3, did not influence the initial rate of H₂O₂ decomposition. A similar change in the concentration of the salt caused an increase in the over-all rate 1.1 to 1.3 times of the previous results (fig. 1). At a salt concentration lower than that given in the experimental procedure, the rate of decomposition was directly proportional to the concentration of the salt catalyst.

Fig.1. Decomposition of H₂O₂ at 60°, expressed by the decrease of its concentration in moles/lit, as a function of time, and

- (A) the catalytic effect of: nickel chloride (Δ), nickel nitrate (O), nickel sulphate ($\bullet$); zinc sulphate (X), sodium sulphate ($\square$), and sodium hydroxide ($\blacktriangle$);
 (B) the combined effect of the salt and 1 ml of 0.1 N NaOH solution.

The rate of decomposition, at a fixed concentration of the salt, was directly proportional to the remaining concentration of undecomposed H₂O₂; thus the decomposition obeyed simply to a 1st-order kinetics with respect to H₂O₂. The Arrhenius plots, which are based on the values of the specific rate constants at various temperatures, are shown in fig 2, and the derived activation energies (E) and changes in entropy of activation (ΔS)* are given in table 1.

TABLE I

Values of E and ΔS^* for the decomposition of H₂O₂ by various salts in absence (a) and presence (p) of NaOH.

Salt	E (Kcal/mole)		Δ_s (e.u)		pH	
	a	p	a	p	a	p
Nickel sulphate	18.4	14.0	-20.7	-36.3	5.0	6.5
Nickel nitrate	18.4	14.0	-27.5	-31.9	4.0	7.0
Nickel chloride	18.4	14.0	-28.2	-33.7	4.0	7.9
Zinc sulphate	19.8	—	-23.0	—	5.0	7.5
Sodium sulphate	—	23.0	—	-8.3	7.0	10.5

It is shown from the data in table 1 that the change in entropy of activation in all cases has negative values, this is probably because the number of the reacting species

* E is used instead of $\Delta H_{\pm}$ in the original equation.

diminishes in the activation process. Moreover, it is found that various nickel salts exert their effects primarily on the entropy of activation, the energy of activation being rather identical within experimental error. A comparatively fast decomposition of H_2O_2 in presence of nickel sulphate is parallel to the less negative value of ΔS^* .

According to the absolute rate theory⁴ the more positive the value of ΔS^* the greater is the value of f^*/f ; where f^* and f are the complete partition function of the activated complex and reactants, thus the greater value of ΔS^* (the less negative one in table I) obtained with nickel sulphate is compatible with an activated complex having more freedom to decompose into the reaction products. If we disregard the slight difference in E values for zinc sulphate and nickel salts (table I), then the variation of rates using various salts could be put similar to the decreasing order of ΔS^* values as: nickel sulphate > zinc sulphate > nickel nitrate > nickel chloride. Decomposition of H_2O_2 in the temperature range 15 to 55°, catalyzed by a mixture of $NiSO_4$ and Na_2MoO_4 , is shown⁵ to be a 1st order reaction having an activation energy of 14-15 Kcal/mole.

Addition of NaOH: When a small quantity of NaOH solution (1 ml of 0.1N) was added to each solution of H_2O_2 in which a certain amount of a salt (0.1 equivalent) was present, the pH of the solutions increased (table I), and the rates of decomposition also changed as seen in fig 1. The decomposition of H_2O_2 occurred with a comparatively fast rate in solutions containing either nickel nitrate or nickel chloride, while nickel sulphate, which was the most active salt for decomposition in the previous experiments, had become the less active salt of nickel in the present experiment. Almost, no decomposition took place when zinc sulphate was present with NaOH, but the rate of decomposition increased substantially by sodium sulphate in case if the rate is compared with previous results when NaOH was absent. The various effects of the added NaOH on the salt catalyzed decomposition of H_2O_2 at 60° are shown in fig 1.

The determined values of E , for H_2O_2 decomposition under the new circumstances, which are also given in table I, are lower by 4.4 Kcal/mole than the corresponding values

Fig. 2. Arrhenius plots for decomposition of H_2O_2 in absence (A) and presence of sodium hydroxide (B). The salts and the symbols as in fig. 1.

4. Glasstone, Laidler and Eyring, 'The Theory of Rate Processes', McGraw-Hill, Co., New York, 1940.
5. Bogdanova, Somanova and Chernyshov, *Izv. Vysshikh Uchon Zavedenil Khim*, 1964, 7, (3), 406.

obtained in the previous experiments which are performed without addition of NaOH. Moreover, the ΔS^* values are more negative in the present case, thus indicating either a greater reduction in the number of the reacting species in the activation process, or probably due to the formation of an activated complex having less degrees of freedom compared with the corresponding complex when NaOH was absent. The increased rate of decomposition when NaOH was added to nickel chloride or nitrate + H_2O_2 solutions is mainly due to the smaller energy barrier ($E=14$ Kcal/mole); thus increasing the value of $e^{-E/RT}$ term while $e^{\Delta S^\ddagger/R}$ was decreasing so that k values in eqn. (1) were considerably higher than the corresponding values obtained without addition of NaOH.

Although the decomposition of H_2O_2 by the combined effect of NaOH and sodium sulphate has an activation energy of 23 Kcal/mole which causes a marked lowering in the value of the exponential term, $e^{-E/RT}$, the rate of decomposition in basic medium was found to be substantially faster. This is attributed to the higher ΔS^* value (-8.3 Kcal/mole. log) in the rate expression; thus indicating the formation of an activated complex which is more free to decompose into the products.

The addition of NaOH to a solution containing only H_2O_2 , in the temperature range 25 to 80°, caused the decomposition of the latter to take place with a rate almost similar to that observed by the catalytic action of nickel sulphate. The previous results of salt + NaOH action could thus be explained as in the following: 1. The salts containing the common $SO_4^{=}$ radical, such as zinc, sodium and nickel sulphates, could be considered to cause a retardation of the catalytic action of NaOH in H_2O_2 decomposition. Zinc sulphate had the greatest retarding effect; the rate of decomposition almost ceased in solutions containing this salt together with NaOH. The retarding effect of sodium sulphate could have been more pronounced if the pH of the solution was kept down at a value lower than 10.5, i.e. at a value closer to those attained with the remaining salts. As the added amount of NaOH, to the experimental solution of H_2O_2 + sodium sulphate, was decreased the rate of decomposition slowed down to a great extent. 2. The influence of nickel chloride and nickel nitrate almost disappeared in the presence of NaOH; the observed rate in the latter case was similar with that detected when only NaOH was present in the peroxide solution.

The various effects of the added NaOH, could also be accounted for on the basis of pH changes of the reaction medium. The rate of the reaction increased when the pH changed from 4 to 7 in cases of nickel chloride and nitrate, or from 7 to 10.5 with sodium sulphate, the rate of decomposition was, in fact, directly dependent on pH . The deaccelerating effect of a salt with increasing values of pH from 4 or 5 to 7 is clearly seen in cases of nickel sulphate and zinc sulphate.

The influence of nickel and zinc salts on H_2O_2 decomposition are in general agreement with result of Picron⁶, who showed that nickel oxide in presence of alkalis increased the rate of decomposition of H_2O_2 , while similar compounds of Zn decreased the rate considerably. Chelate compounds of nickel and zinc behaved similar to nickel oxide and zinc oxide respectively⁷. Another work on the catalytic role of various ions in decomposing

6. Picron, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, France, 1949, 754-8.

7. Koier, Alikina and Troitskaya, *Akad. Nauk Kaz*, S S R, 1962, 342-6.

H_2O_2 showed⁸ that the combination $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2 + \text{Cu}^{+2} + \text{Fe}^{+3}$ was more effective than $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ (prepared from NiSO_4 and NaOH), and that the order of addition of the ions was found to be more significant in this respect. A mechanism was discussed whereby the Cu^{+2} or Fe^{+3} ions were adsorbed on the $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ with the formation of donor-radical complexes with quasi-free electrons. The reaction, in all cases, was shown to be 1st-order with respect to H_2O_2 .

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